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Ethics and Aesthetics in Contemporary Art(AI a Free Information and Independent Thought)

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Abstract: *Technology that augurs a revolution in human entanglement. Artificial Intelligence (AI) machines that can perform tasks requiring human intelligence have rapidly become a reality. For epochs, humanity has occupied itself with exploring reality and the quest for knowledge. Humanity has experienced technological changes throughout history. However, technology has rarely fundamentally transformed our societies' social and political structure.*

AI and other emerging technologies seem to be moving human skills closer to knowing reality beyond the confines of our perception. AI's role is moderating. AI-generated art and its consequences, poses for artists in broad societies are reshaping the ethical and aesthetic development. The fundamental questions that arise from this context are about the effect of technological evolution on the creative thinking abilities of the digitally enhanced generation. What are the mental and social challenges that accompany contemporary art and how have they been innovative in the world of reason and logic?

Keywords: *art, artworks, art piece, philosophy, AI, human cognition, artists, reality, consciousness, knowledge, creativity, aesthetics, wisdom, individual thought, AI-generated art, distinction, technology, entanglement, humanity, moderating, perception, consequences, ethical, evolution, reason, logic*

Research Objective:

How can we reflect and shape our relationship with Artificial Intelligence?

Research question:

What are the ethical concerns surrounding the generation of art by artificial art?

Introduction:

“Our soul is made for thinking, that is for perceiving” (P. Montesquieu)

In this atmosphere of intellectual challenges, once axiomatic concepts generate the existence of physical reality, the eternal nature of ethics. The power to understand, think, and judge the method of purpose for interacting with the environment.

According to Kant's account, human reason could know reality deeply. Human cognition and experience filter, structure, and distort all that we know, even when we attempt to reason 'purely' by logic alone. Objectives reality in the strictest sense__ what Kant called the thing—in—itself is ever present but inherently beyond our direct knowledge.

The human mind relies on conceptual thinking and lived experiences, it could never achieve the degree of pure thought required to know this inner essence of things.

We entered the world of AI information when information is contextualized, it becomes knowledge. When knowledge has complex convictions, it becomes wisdom and the digital world has little patience for wisdom, its values are shaped by approbation, not introspection.

The introduction of AI-generated art which completes the sentences, we are texting identifies the book or images we are seeking, and intuits articles and entertainment we might enjoy based on prior ethics has often seemed applied to more mundane than revolutionary. But as it is being applied to more elements of our lives, it is altering the role that our minds have traditionally played in shaping, ordering, and assessing our choices and actions.

We are in a world of technologies that tell us to ‘speak’ which completely reshaping our minds, and learning the way we socialize. We are experiencing a hyperconnected reality that modules our digital culture and affects ethical cognitive and particularly human skill and creative developments, whereas social reality is represented in artworks.

The AI gradation is radically smacking the human condition in profound ways:

1. Cognitive, ethical, and aesthetical aspects of contemporary representation of art.
2. Distinction between machine and human creativity
3. Virtual augmented and reality complexity

In this adaptation, creativity has been conceded as one of the most important human skills to face the convulsion brought by the age of AI varies with the task, it performs so, too must the techniques developers use to create that AI. This is the fundamental challenge of deploying machine learning, different goals, functions required, and different training techniques. This technique is called supervised learning because AI developers use a dataset containing.

Developers have used supervised learning techniques for many purposes, such as recognizing images. It has become a democratic essential requirement for re-generating useful ideas and images and getting the superiority offered by AI ethical or unethical.

The purposes that arise from this context are about the outcomes of the AI evolution on the creative thinking faculties of the digitally magnified community. How does creativity articulate correspondingly to digital art changes? What are the advantages and disadvantages of the contemporary art world?

The main objective of this research is to highlight some preparatory reflections about the commute that the AI evolution of our millennium is a compression on human creativity, particularly on contemporary art. The analysis of the social reality represented in artwork, but also constitutes both logic and reason. Logically refers to processes and reasoning for the existence of knowledge, which is an integral part of every artwork.

With one exception artists had a high degree of resistance. This hasn't aged well. Today over 20 billion images have been generated by AI. The results are captivating and speak for themselves but they also stirred aspects of the ethics of aesthetics, which creates diversity and inclusivity in the artwork.

The fact that AI operates according to its processes, which are different from and often faster than human mental processes, adds another complexity. AI develops its approaches for fulfilling whatever objective functions were specified. It produces outcomes and answers that are not characteristically human and that are largely independent of its own cultures. With the global nature of the digital world, these digital contextualizations have entered a new realm of abstraction without knowing the philosophical and ethical aspects of aesthetics.

The Digital Adaptation:

The creeping fear that human creativity which we had for so long believed to be uniquely ours, is being encroached upon. You might not know how to feel about AI art. Artists and art critics would take a lot of pride in critiquing and distinguishing a piece of art produced by a human or by AI. Pointing out the obvious difference of 8 fingers on one hand and 2 on the other. However as our world is ever evolving, so is AI, and it has modified itself to the extent that it has become increasingly difficult to differentiate between a real art piece and a digitally manufactured one. It may seem like magic, but in reality, this is the result of an incredibly resource-intensive process. AI may start as a blank slate, but once trained it can construct anything of value. Describing its undertakings as a 'trained' software is an understatement even, because the way that AI trains and that humans train are extremely different. The AI will showcase a beautiful image for the human gaze, but it feeds upon sophisticated combinations of numbers to give the desired outcomes. Those values could represent the color of a single pixel or the direction of a curved line. The AI's goal is to identify quantitative patterns between these number values and the text characters, which are the words we use to describe the image we wish to receive. And these patterns may not even be comprehensible to us, since we do not have any words for them. AI companies gather training data in front of a database of hundreds and millions of images with textual input. These databases scour the internet for such input, be it from social media posts, their captions or descriptions, etc. Next, when it is time to generate the actual image, the AI doesn't simply just combine the collected data, because keep in mind it does not own a copy of those original images from which it has collected data. Instead, it starts with the complete and random noise, and gradually over many interactions, it will reorganize that numerical and textual data into pixels by the desired patterns that wish to be achieved. Thus a completely new image will be produced.

Ethical Usage of AI:

Now that you understand the gist of how AI images are formed, the million-dollar question is 'How to use it?' Well, the most common way is via text, prompting you to throw in a bunch of phrases, describing what you want the AI software to create. It may not however give you the exact outcomes that you hoped to achieve, because one must remember that AI has no concept of what, per se, short curly hair is. It just knows that this textual phrase tends to be associated with the patterns in the color values that have been incorporated into its database.

That is why generative AI can behave in ways that we find strange, ways a human would never behave. We can control a lot of the fine details of what is being generated, but as the saying goes, everything has a limit. Even things that may seem infinite, end up being finite in some way and contain many limitations. For instance, there are many complications regarding copyright laws, and if AI can be accused of stealing and reproducing images without artists' consent. That's why many Getty Images, a database of copyrighted stock photos, recently filed a lawsuit against an AI-generated image, as it was producing fake photos in the Getty Images style, reproducing details as small as legible watermarks. The court is still indecisive on whether this was a legal use of copyrighted images, but it all depends on how they interpret 'fair use'.

These may be categorized under any of the following:

1. Transformative
2. Effect on market
3. Subjective

The 'fair use' clause in the US protects you if you are using someone else's copyrighted artwork for your purposes, but it only protects you under certain circumstances. There are unofficially five factors that are taken into account, but I'll be drilling down on the three core ones.

First and foremost, the new work that is being primarily produced, must be transformative. That means it should be adding values that the original artwork did not provide through additional expressional meaning or insight.

Secondly, it shouldn't be damaging to the original copyright owner's income. There could be a real measurable impact on income or just taking away from their potential market.

Thirdly, the judge always has discretion, and it is truly up to them to determine whether they believe that one case of fair use is good or bad. So should fair use apply to AI as well? Well, according to the aforementioned list, is it transformative? I would first make a clear distinction between AI and the art it is set to generate. There are many ways that AI can be manipulated if one wishes to influence the process of generating an AI art piece. Each point of contact with a human in that process is an opportunity for the user to add meaning in a way that the AI is technically incapable of achieving. This confirms that art can be transformative. The issue is AI itself. The AI is a direct product of these copyrighted works, and it is not an artwork that it produces, it is a mere tool that aids in the process of producing said art piece. This means that AI does not inherently have any meaning of expression or empathy that an artist must have. It does not provide us with any emotional insight. This is not a surprise considering how it analyzes patterns, and that essentially is its entitled job. But in reality, these analyzed patterns are incomprehensible to the human mind.

Furthermore, it can be damaging to the original copyrighted owner's potential income. Take Adobe Firefly for instance, and their new generative AI service. You can provide it with an artist's name, and it will produce images in their unique and iconic style. This put it in direct competition with the original artist from who inspiration was taken. So why would one commission an expensive custom-made artwork when they can buy a much cheaper service and generate many more images?

Third is the fundamental subjective question of whether this act is good or bad. There is no right answer to this in truth, but I implore you to consider that fair use was put into place to protect and encourage creativity. Allowing AI companies to scrape and train on whatever they want without getting the artist's consent incentivizes artists to not be creative in the first place and then not even post their artwork online.

AI & Copyright Laws:

As much as creating an original art piece is important, it is equally necessary to copyright your piece to avoid it from being illegally copied and profited from, which puts you at a disadvantage. Even if an artist does not copyright their work, what is legal to do and what is ethical are two completely independent questions. A lot of times laws are just constantly catching up to ethics, and a lot of times it is considered impractical for artists to obtain copyright on their work. To some artists, this may not seem like much to them but it really matters to someone who is drawing every day and it is generally their primary or even secondary source of income. Therefore such an important step in the creation of a piece is not a concern for a student or a hobbyist who does not receive much income from their art. Just because anyone cannot afford legal protection, it certainly does not mean that it is right to breach the boundaries that they have set. That is what falls under ethics.

Continuing to use AI under such circumstances just proves how we keep disrespecting artists, which will inevitably not end well or be sustainable for AI companies. However, it is equally difficult now to distinguish between an original piece and an AI-generated one. When you zoom into either one online, you will end up viewing the color palette in tiny pixels or boxes, and it thus becomes impossible to differentiate between the two. What is real, and what is pretending to be real?

Empowering Creativity:

This is the worst ending for both AI companies and artists if AI figures out how to take charge of its creative sense. If that happens it will lead to the ultimate doom of human creativity and self-independent thought. Humans will simply cease to take charge of innovation and new ideas, leaving it all to AI to deal with and reproduce. With the current question of AI's legality of copying artists' work, it will soon degrade the potential of actual artists which will also limit any emotional connection to art pieces that viewers would have.

In contrast, AI could serve as a helping hand to artists on various projects, as some are currently making use of it. A personal anecdote was when I would realize that a painting I was making appeared to be very pixelated, and the only solution would be to create a brand new piece on a new surface of large size and redraw the entire thing. However, new professional illustration software like Clip Studio has AI upscaling that will do this automatically, saving you the trouble of going through the entire painting process again. This will not only save your time but your material cost as well as energy efficiency. Additionally one could also preview a specific color palette before actually committing to it. Just mark down what colors you want, and approximately where, and it will produce something that will let you feel the vibe of a palette before you commit to it.

Ideally, we reap the benefits of creativity without abusing the resources we use. I believe that this is possible if legal regulation takes the side of the artist more than it does now. To achieve this, the two principles must be respected. First, AI companies should be required to obtain consent from an artist before using their artworks for training and as a result of this, companies will need some way of compensating artists for their work. This can be through contracts such as licensing agreements. But in the future AI could be another tool in an artist's workshop, freeing up their hands from tedious tasks and allowing them to focus more on just being creative.

Conclusion:

Humans can take what I have explained as a guide, and adjust their search engine accordingly. However, they still may not be able to explain why one particular page is ranked higher than another. To achieve greater convenience and accuracy, human developers have had to willingly forgo a measure of direct understanding of empathy and consciousness.

Works of art must be judged based on aesthetics. By analyzing the coherence of its form, and then the symbolic value of the 'world' it paints or suggests to us and of the image of the human relations reflected.

The central concern of an ethical analysis is not whether the work can be evaluated positively or negatively in ethical terms, but instead resides in the more complex question of the aesthetic manifestation of the ethical dimension of the work of art. Ethical concerns, in Greek, are the search for a good 'way of being for a wise course of action.' On this account, ethics is part of a philosophy that organizes practical existence around the representation of the 'good'.

"Search for beauty itself just like a home for yourself, where you belong to, which is a self-involved thing. Aesthetic judgment is a fundamental part of our everyday lives. We're making it all the time."

We are in a world of such complexity and inherent incalculability, where AI introduces another possible source of misinterpretation. AI and other emerging technologies seem to be moving humans close to knowing reality beyond the confines of our perception. Ultimately, however, we may discover that even these technologies have limits. Our problem is that we have not yet grasped their philosophical implications. We are increasingly becoming more advanced by them, but not consciously or cautiously. In recent times, new technology has been developed but remains in dire need of a guiding philosophy.

According to Kant's account;

'Immanuel Kant opened the preface to his critique of pure reason with an observation:

"Human reason has the peculiar fate in one species of its cognitions that it is burdened with questions which it cannot dismiss, since they are given to it as problems by the nature of reason itself, but which it also cannot answer, since they transcend every capacity of human reason."

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